

Decoding Sensitive Data Management

Simplifying the Australian sensitive
research data management
landscape for institutions

This document, herein referred to as ‘the Decoder’, was developed as part of the [ARDC’s Institutional Underpinnings](#) project ‘Building a Decoder ring for sensitive data’ and was produced as a collaborative effort by members of the Steering Committee.

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While the Steering Committee used their institutional perspectives and experiences in the development of the Decoder, their views do not necessarily represent the views of the institution and their institutional affiliation should not be seen as endorsement by these Institutions.

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Definitions

Many of the concepts discussed within the Decoder have no formal or consistent definition. The list provided below is intended to clarify the usage of these terms in the context of the Decoder.

Sensitive research data: Data that, due to its nature or content, carries inherent risks if disclosed, misused, or inadequately protected. This includes data that may impact the privacy, well-being, safety, or rights of individuals or groups; threaten ecological balance, cultural heritage, or national security; or have significant economic, ethical, or intellectual property implications. Note that this may differ from more narrow definitions used in the Privacy Act 1988 (Cth) or other jurisdiction's definition of "sensitive information".

Data sharing: Sharing data with a specific audience, often involving a data sharing agreement that specifies conditions regarding use, access, timeframe, authorship and reuse.

Data publishing: Making research data available to others for reuse, either openly or under certain conditions such as a licence, usually via a repository.

Data licensing: The legal terms and conditions that govern the access and use of research data.

Data reuse: The use of existing data for new purposes, such as analysis, synthesis, or validation.

Data residency: The physical or geographical location of data or information.

Data jurisdiction: The legal authority that a country or region has over data stored within its boundaries where the key factor is the location (residency) of the data.

Data sovereignty: Similar to data jurisdiction, but also takes into account the origin of the data. *Indigenous data sovereignty* refers to the rights of the Indigenous people or community to self-govern their data, regardless of residency or jurisdiction.

Data governance: The cross-functional framework for handling data that specifies decision making rights and responsibilities, formalises data policies, standards and procedures and monitors compliance.

Introduction

Sensitive research data includes any information that, due to its nature or content, carries inherent risks if disclosed, misused, or inadequately protected. This includes data that may impact the privacy, well-being, safety, or rights of individuals or groups; threaten ecological balance, cultural heritage, or national security; or have significant economic, ethical, or intellectual property implications. The management and protection of sensitive research data is influenced and informed by a complex landscape of recommendations and requirements.

Australian academic and research institutions operate within a complex web of regulatory and governance standards, especially when it comes to the creation and management of research data. The cornerstone of these are research-specific guidelines ([summarised here](#)) that promote ethical and responsible conduct of research, developed or endorsed by the Australian Research Council (ARC), the National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC), and Universities Australia (UA)¹⁻⁶. These include the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research (the Code)⁶, the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (the National Statement)⁵ and several frameworks and standards to support research with and about Indigenous peoples^{1,2,4,7}. These guides not only delineate the ethical principles underpinning research but also prescribe standards for research data management and governance that need to be considered alongside other mandatory regulations.

Institutions must also navigate the complex requirements of state and federal legislation that impact the generation and management of research data, particularly in areas of data protection, privacy, and security. The Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)⁸, for instance, sets out stringent principles regarding the handling of personal information, adding another layer of responsibility to data governance. The complexity multiplies when research projects extend across borders. For example, studies involving collaboration with European entities may also be subject to directives like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁹. This means that Australian institutions must not only adhere to local laws but also understand and comply with relevant international regulatory frameworks. In addition, the Security of Critical Infrastructure Act 2018 (Cth)¹⁰ (SOCI Act) and its recent amendments have created obligations on how research data is protected and how incidents are managed, and the Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022 (Cth)¹¹ (DAT Act) has highlighted some of the complexity that can arise from collaboration and sharing of third-party research data.

Furthermore, as cyber threats escalate on a global scale, universities are required to improve their security posture by aligning with both Australian and international cybersecurity frameworks. The Australian Government's Information Security Manual (ISM)¹² offers directives on technology and protocol, ensuring the secure processing of information. Additionally, many institutions also implement internationally recognised standards such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) frameworks¹³, or ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴, which provide overarching frameworks for information security management for specific environments (usually those holding sensitive research data). These standards, though beneficial, compound the complexity by introducing a myriad of requirements and considerations that secure and restrict data access, many of which conflict with FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data principles¹⁵ and the collaborative, exploratory, or reuse elements of research practice.

These frameworks, governance instruments and regulatory requirements are designed to safeguard privacy, ensure data integrity, and maintain public trust in research. However, navigating the intricate landscape requirements can be an overwhelming endeavour for researchers and institutional

decision makers. The Australian Research Data Commons Research Data Management Framework for Institutions (2023) report¹⁶ identified that there was no formal or consistent data classification scheme used across Australian tertiary institutions, or standardised methods to identify or protect 'sensitive' data. Institutions are left to independently navigate this complex governance landscape, and to integrate these requirements with their own internal policies and procedures.

This diversity of approaches is further confounded by the fact that there is no single 'owner' of the problem within institutional structures. As part of this project, we surveyed approaches to core elements of sensitive data management at six Australian institutions, and developed a report entitled 'Current institutional approaches to sensitive research data management'¹⁷, herein referred to as the 'Landscape Report'. This report clearly highlighted the existing complexities in the decision-making landscape around sensitive research data at Australian institutions - where **the full scope of decision making around sensitive data management is rarely the responsibility of one individual**. Rather the problem is divided across multiple roles such as the Chief Information Officer (CIO), Chief Data Officer (CDO), Deputy Vice-Chancellor Research (DVC-R), Pro-Vice-Chancellor Research Infrastructure (PVC-RI), or Chief Information Security Officer (CISO).

Problem statement: Researchers and institutions face a complex mix of ethical, legal, and technical recommendations and requirements for managing sensitive research data.

Additionally, each element of institutional decision making can be the responsibility of a different role or individual, leading to potential confusion, risk of non-compliance, and inefficiencies.

A unified 'Decoder' is needed to simplify and consolidate these guidelines for effective data governance, and to ensure cohesive decision making across all institutional roles.

The 'Decoder' Concept

The purpose of this project was to begin to 'decode' the complex governance landscape impacting the management of sensitive research data in Australia, in a format that could be interpreted by the many institutional decision makers who need to understand and comply with these requirements.

The complexity of the instruments, the ever-changing governance landscape, and the subjective nature of their implementation means there is no way to simply harmonise all the requirements. Instead, we aimed to break down this complex array of data protections and controls into core thematic areas, and to provide examples of the spectrum of understandable and actionable controls that can be used to safeguard data.

This 'Decoder' is not designed to be another framework that institutions need to comply with. Instead, it is a tool to clarify existing requirements and provide decision-makers with consistent guidelines on the management and protection of different classes of data, ensuring data are handled with the requisite care, security, and integrity. By simplifying the intricate landscape of frameworks, legislation, and best practice recommendations, the Decoder identifies the main controls and considerations that apply to sensitive research data, and any additional protections or enhancements that can be used to strengthen these protections. This allows institutions to consider any given scenario and determine the baseline requirements as well as any enhancements that can feasibly be implemented to provide the level of protection that aligns with their risk appetite.

The Decoder is intended to bridge the gap between vast regulatory landscapes and actionable steps, making it easier to determine the right controls for sensitive data. Additionally, by centralising this information, the Decoder addresses the institutional structural challenge, where multiple stakeholders hold different elements of responsibility. By presenting a holistic view of the potential data protection requirements, **the Decoder can help break down barriers between legal, technical, ethical, and administrative domains**, allowing for a more unified approach to data governance. Presenting the spectrum of controls and requirements in the Decoder format helps provide a common language that fosters interdisciplinary cooperation, ensuring that all stakeholders (from the researchers to the CIO, CISO or DVC-R) are informed, aligned, and empowered to make collective, robust decisions that advance research while safeguarding sensitive information.

The Decoder is a starting point towards developing a central reference for institutions and researchers, simplifying the complexities of the numerous frameworks, governance tools, and legislative requirements affecting research data management. However, as the governance landscape around sensitive research data continues to evolve, the information in the Decoder will also need to adapt and update. This tool not only aids in enhancing an institution's ability to protect research data and confidently engage in collaboration on projects that include sensitive data, but also serves as a roadmap for improving data management maturity.

Data Classification

As noted in the Australian Research Data Commons [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#) (2023) report¹⁶ the starting point for any cross-institutional collaboration or recommendations about the handling or protection of sensitive research data needs to begin with a clear and consistent Data Classification Framework. A clear classification framework is vital for defining ‘sensitive’ data.

This project is utilising a variant of the Data Classification Framework developed by Monash University and the University of Tasmania as part of the ARDC’s [Institutional Underpinnings Phase 1 projects](#) shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The Data Classification Framework

The framework is designed with a simple, ordinal structure that uses a colour gradient (Green to Red) rather than subjective text labels, to classify data on a scale of risk.

The classification framework used here can be mapped against any ordinal framework. The distinction between Yellow, Orange and Red data is primarily based on risk. Similarly, even a three-tiered classification can be applied, by collapsing two of the bands. Unpublished research data can span the spectrum from Yellow through to Red, and the distinction between the classes is at the discretion of the institution, aligned with their risk appetite. The various forms of a classification framework at Australian institutions are outlined in the Landscape Report¹⁷. Regardless of the classification framework used by an institution, there exists a spectrum of risk within ‘sensitive data’, from adverse impacts on an individual or institution through to severe or catastrophic impacts. That spectrum is reflected within the controls outlined in this document. The benefits of using a data classification include:

Risk Prioritisation

The colour-coded tiers from green to red enable quick identification and prioritisation of data based on their risk levels. This is critical in environments where a wide array of data types and sensitivities exist. Knowing what constitutes a higher risk allows for targeted allocation of resources, such as tighter security controls or additional ethics oversight, towards the most sensitive (Red) data.

Clarity and Consistency

The ordinal, colour-based classification replaces subjective text labels, thereby reducing ambiguity. This ensures that stakeholders from various disciplines—such as researchers, IT professionals, or university administrators—have a consistent understanding of sensitivity or risk rather than needing to know anything about data structure, intended use, or governance. This shared understanding is vital for effective interdisciplinary collaboration and cross-domain decision making.

Operational Efficiency

Having a clear initial classification helps streamline operational processes. With the risk level of the data clearly marked, stakeholders and decision makers can swiftly determine what level of security is needed, what ethical considerations must be factored in, and what legal requirements are applicable. This speeds up decision-making and reduces administrative load.

Defining 'Sensitive' Data

Based on the classification framework, sensitive data begins at Orange and extends into Red. This range highlights the need to understand the baseline controls that should be applied to protect sensitive data, as well as situations where significant enhancements are required to protect data classified as Red or 'highly sensitive'.

How to interpret the Decoder

The Decoder takes the breadth and complexity of the Australian research data governance landscape, including all the major governance instruments that impact institutional decision making around research data management, and splits the requirements or actionable content into core thematic elements – such as “Privacy, Ethics, and Data Residency” or “Physical Security”. Within each of these elements is a series of thematic domains that capture the most common implementations or requirements that appear across different governance instruments. The controls are presented in the form of practical applications and shown in the format of ‘baseline control or recommendation’ and then any ‘enhancements’ that can be applied for additional protection of higher risk or Red data.

Methodology used to develop the Decoder

To develop the Decoder, we undertook a systematic analysis of governance instruments and cyber security frameworks relevant to sensitive research data management. These included Australian research specific guidance such as the Code¹⁻⁶, Indigenous data sovereignty principles^{1,2,7}, federal legislative requirements related to data such as the Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)⁸, and Australian and multi-jurisdictional cyber security frameworks – primarily the ISM¹², NIST¹³ and ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴. Requirements related to external jurisdictions such as GDPR¹⁴, or state-specific legislation was considered out of scope – however these kinds of jurisdictional nuance do not alter the core structure, they mostly add additional detail to existing considerations (such as privacy or data retention). The complete list of governance instruments considered is provided in Appendix 1.

Our methodology entailed a thorough review each governance instrument to identify the core recommendations related to sensitive data within each, followed by a synthesis of these diverse sources to refine overlapping recommendations into defined elements. This process identified six core elements:

- Privacy, Ethics, and Data Residency
- Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse
- Cyber Security – Protection and Prevention
- Cyber Security – Detection and Response
- Cyber Security – Maintenance and Governance
- Physical Security

Each element was further dissected to extract fundamental themes and specific guidance on managing sensitive data encompassed by that element, across all the relevant governance instruments. For example, ‘**Perimeters, access controls, and monitoring**’, ‘**Behavioural approaches**’ and ‘**Policies/procedures and documented processes**’ were the three core themes identified within the Physical Security element. For each of these themes we identified the main baseline recommendations for standard data protection and any recommended enhancements tailored to elevate the security posture around highly sensitive data.

This information is presented within the decoder as:

- **Main dot point** for the baseline or primary recommendation in the theme
 - + **Plus sign indented dot point** for enhancements that can be applied to the above, to strengthen protections or when working with highly sensitive or Red data

Additional considerations

Different classes of data sensitivity provide the scaffold onto which controls and protections can be applied, however since *the Decoder is a guidance document rather than a specific framework*, the mapping of implementable protections to different levels of sensitivity are a mixture of recommendations and baseline requirements. Whether enhancements need to be applied will depend on the risk appetite of the institution and the feasibility of applying them in the context under consideration.

Institutions and researchers can use the Decoder as a guide to evaluate their current baseline maturity across different elements of sensitive data management. By showcasing the areas within the diverse governance instrument that are most relevant to research data, institutions can determine the range of actionable improvements to target to satisfy their risk appetite. Collating the breadth of controls or requirements that impact the whole of research data management, from legal and governance through to physical and cyber security, allows institutional decision makers to see the impact of their decision-making domain within the wider landscape of data governance constraints and requirements.

Privacy, Ethics, and Data Residency

In the context of Australian research data, recommendations and controls relating to ‘Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency’ are governed by a suite of Australian legislative and research-specific guidelines. These include legal instruments such as the Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)⁸ and the corresponding Australian Privacy Principles (APPs)¹⁸, as well as comprehensive research-specific guidance provided by the NHMRC and ARC; including the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research⁶ and the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research⁵. Complementing and building on these are guidelines designed to facilitate ethical and empowering research involving Indigenous participants such as the AIATSIS code of ethics², the Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and communities: Guidelines for researchers and stakeholders⁴, and the CARE (collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility and ethics) principles⁷. Overlaying all of these legal instruments and guidance documents are rigorous cyber security frameworks such as the Australian ISM¹², ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴ or NIST, which provide the required controls to ensure rigorous data protection.

Guidelines related to ‘Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency’ are intended to ensure the respectful, ethical, and secure management of research data, particularly when it involves high sensitivity or potentially vulnerable populations. The guidelines can be divided into four thematic areas: **data collection and integrity**, **privacy and confidentiality**, **data residency and jurisdiction**, and **data retention and disposal**. Additionally relevant to the governance instruments in this element are considerations around access, use and disclosure of data that are comprehensively covered by [Cyber Security: Protection and Prevention](#) and [Data Sharing, Licensing, and Usage Rights](#).

It is important to note that some state-based legislation, as well as privacy or cultural considerations from other jurisdictions (such as the GDPR⁹), are not included here but may also impact choices around research data management. Institutions should determine that all relevant governance instruments have been considered.

Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency: **Data Collection and Integrity**

Ensuring accurate, ethical, and complete gathering of research data while preserving its authenticity and reliability.

- Support researchers to ensure data collection methodologies are robust, well documented, and limited to data that is necessary and relevant for the research.
 - + Implement robust internal auditing to ensure these processes are being followed.
 - + Ensure regular review of sensitive research, such as progress reports and any amendments required, by the relevant ethics, governance, community, or oversight committee.
 - + Highly sensitive data or projects classified as Red may require regular review by a project-specific governance or steering committee.
- Ensure data and information used in research are accurate, complete, reliable, and stored securely. Enhancements for highly sensitive/Red data include:
 - + Provide access to systems with inbuilt and auditable data integrity checking (such as checksums, hash functions or digital signatures) to detect changes or degradation in the data.
 - + Utilise version control systems to track changes to datasets over time.

- + Ensure the secure storage of data following processes outlined in [Cyber Security – Protection and Prevention](#) and [Physical Security](#) also maintains the integrity of the data.
 - + Increase the frequency and depth of data audit trails or data traceability, recording more granular details about data access and modification.
- Provide transparency about how data is collected, used, and disclosed. Ensure accountability at all levels of the organisation. This will include:
 - + Regular communication with individuals or communities about how their data is being used, from protocol development, obtaining ethics approval, recruitment of participants through to project completion.
 - + Where a community, culture or group of people may be represented, particularly if they are considered vulnerable or the grouping is of a sensitive nature, representatives from those communities, cultures or groups of people should be involved in the development and implementation of the data collection process.
 - + Ensuring processes are in place for researchers to follow NHMRC guidelines⁴⁻⁶ to obtain clear, explicit, and informed consent for the collection and use of sensitive personal data when required, including data reuse considerations (see [Data Publishing and Reuse](#)).
 - + Establish a clear chain of custody for data, detailing who accessed it, when, and for what purpose.
 - + Support the creation of a data dictionary to ensure only data that is necessary to answer the research question is collected. The data dictionary should define key variables, units, and specific data attributes to support transparency, but will also assist with reproducibility and interoperability (see below).
 - Support researchers to document their data using existing metadata standards that are relevant to the research discipline, but may include the date of collection, collection methodology, ethics approval details, lead investigator, and access to any data dictionary that has been created.
 - + If the metadata also contains sensitive information, ensure it is managed using the same protocols as the primary data.
 - + Data interoperability and reproducibility can be further supported by providing a data dictionary that defines the key variables, units, and specific data attributes.
 - Ensure data collected from or about Indigenous peoples or communities is collected and managed in line with CARE data principles⁷ and the relevant Australian research integrity guidelines^{1,2,4} including ensuring data collection and subsequent use result in a tangible benefit to Indigenous communities and acknowledging that Indigenous peoples and communities have the right to make decisions about their data. The practical implementation of these principles will vary greatly by context; however, some example enhancements include:
 - + Establishing regular two-way communication between the research project and the Indigenous participants ensuring any changes in the research direction are communicated and agreed upon.
 - + Facilitating ongoing consultation and communication by establishing an Indigenous data governance advisory role or committee in the wider research process.
 - + Establish regular reviews of how and where Indigenous data and knowledge is being used.

Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency: **Privacy and Confidentiality**

Protecting personal and sensitive data from unauthorised access, disclosure, or misuse, in line with legislative requirements.

- Have a clear privacy policy and ensure ethics processes and participant information is aligned with any institutional privacy policy, including that participants are informed about their rights and how their data will be used, and that only necessary data is collected. Additional consideration may be needed in the following areas:
 - + Privacy principles generally support collecting only necessary sensitive data and purging it once its purpose is achieved, however in the research context there are additional data retention requirements that need to be considered, as noted in [Data Retention and Destruction](#).
 - + Support researchers to implement data separation strategies, separating and limiting access to personally identifiable data subsets or applying anonymisation or pseudo-anonymisation methods for data sharing and collaboration.
 - + Implement tools to detect and prevent data breaches, such as intrusion detection systems (as discussed in [Cyber Security – Detection and Response](#)) and methods for secure storage and transmission (such as data encryption as covered in [Cyber Security – Protection and Prevention](#)).
- Have a data breach procedure/response plan in place for responding to data breaches, in this case specifically those relating to personal data. The procedure should include processes and clear roles and responsibilities for identifying the breach, containing it, assessing the risk, notifying the affected individuals, and reviewing the incident to prevent future breaches (in alignment with the Notifiable Data Breaches scheme⁸ or relevant state legislation). The procedure should be formally endorsed by senior management and be available to all persons who may need to respond to a data breach.
 - + Regularly test and update the data breach response plan (at least annually) by including staff and researchers in tabletop exercises designed to test all stages of the breach response.
 - + Provide training to staff, including researchers, on how to identify and respond to a data breach.
 - + For research involving personal data, consider securely storing participant contact information in a secondary location to support the notification of participants where the primary data may be inaccessible (i.e. crypto-locked, quarantined etc).
 - + Provide targeted cyber awareness training to researchers working with personally identifiable data, to reduce the risk of breaches but also to reduce the response time before a cyber-attack or breach is identified.

Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency: **Data Residency and Jurisdiction**

Data residency refers to the physical or geographical location of data or information. Data residency considerations can be influenced by legal, policy, or governance mandates that require data to be stored in a specific country or region. Data jurisdiction is the legal authority that a country or region has over data stored within its boundaries where the key factor is the location (residency) of the data. Data sovereignty, however, goes beyond the physical location of data, it also takes into account the origin of the data. Indigenous data sovereignty refers to the rights of the community to self-govern their data, regardless of residency or jurisdiction. Data jurisdiction and sovereignty have varying definitions so the above clarifies their use in this document.

Data residency is a crucial factor to consider when using third-party service providers that offer any data storage or data holding capability, as it can affect the jurisdictional and cultural rights surrounding data. This is particularly important when data is sourced from Indigenous or local communities and applies to more than just personal information.

- Be aware of and comply with residency or sovereignty laws that may impact where certain data types must reside – such as the Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)⁸ and corresponding Notifiable Data Breaches scheme, as well as both national and state-based Acts such as those related to the management of health record data.
 - + Have legal agreements in place when international data transfers are necessary, ensuring the recipient adheres to similar data protection standards.
- Consider the impact of data residency on the rights of individuals or communities to govern their own data, in line with CARE data principles⁷ and AIATSIS² guidelines, to ensure that decisions about data residency do not impact the rights of Indigenous peoples and communities to make decisions about their data.
 - + Engage with communities to understand their specific needs and concerns in terms of data residency. Implement local hosting solutions for sensitive data to reduce any external jurisdictional obligations.
- For research involving data collected from other jurisdictions, ensure awareness of and compliance with any relevant laws of the country where the data is collected, stored, processed, or transferred. For example, data collected on people located in the European Union must comply with the data handling requirements of the GDPR⁹, including the ‘right to be forgotten’ which can have a significant impact on the quality of longitudinal research and the logistics of data management in environments designed to retain not destroy data.
 - + Provide researchers with access to specialised legal advice where there are complex residency or sovereignty concerns.
- Ensure clarity on where the data physically resides, especially when using cloud storage providers or any third-party solutions hosting data (such a survey tools). If using third-party storage solutions, ensure their practices align with the relevant data sovereignty laws and best practices for sensitive data. Enhancements include:
 - + Utilise storage or service solutions that keep data within legal jurisdictions relevant to the research (such as within Australian borders or even within-state restrictions).
 - + Implement restrictions on where *all* data, including backups, can be geographically located.
 - + Outline data residency considerations in contractual agreements with third parties.
 - + For highly sensitive data or data with extreme residency or sovereignty constraints, it may be necessary to utilise secure research environments for collaboration that do not allow data export, or for external collaborators from other jurisdictions to travel to the data storage location rather than exporting or sharing the data.

Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency: **Data Retention and Destruction**

Data retention and destruction are critical aspects of research data governance, ensuring that data is kept securely for as long as it is needed and disposed of appropriately when required. While general records have clear retention timeframes for operational or statutory reasons, research data has distinct and sometimes conflicting retention constraints based on factors such as funding rules, research integrity and transparency requirements, principles of data reuse, ethics and/or consent constraints, unique value, and regulatory obligations. The unique aspect for Australian research data is that minimum retention timeframes for research data (for example clinical trials, genomics data, or research that has community or historical value) are often far longer than those specified by statutory requirements for business records and information. This, combined with the ethos of data reuse and FAIR data practices can lead to a tension between operational (data destruction) and research (data preservation) processes.

- Establish a clear retention policy that details the minimum retention period for different data types. This will be influenced by statutory requirements (which can also vary by state), funding agreements, and institutional policies.
 - + Provide additional layers of support for the retention of sensitive data beyond the minimum statutory requirements that does not conflict with privacy, ethics, or consent requirements. This might involve periodic reviews by data custodians to ensure data protection and integrity, and the provision of secure long-term data storage and data archiving infrastructure.
 - + Regularly review and update data retention policies.
- Ensure any recommendations for data destruction not only comply with minimum retention guidelines but also with the principles of future research value and reuse, as well as research integrity and accountability.
 - + Where data destruction is required, implement secure data destruction processes or services for sensitive data, such as secure erasure or physical destruction.
 - + Obtain a certificate of destruction from any third party responsible for data destruction (including destruction of physical media as well as data deletion).

Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse

‘Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse’ are important aspects of Australian research data management. Data sharing has two elements, referred to herein as ‘data sharing’ (specific audience, often time-bound agreements), and ‘data publishing’ (making research data available to others for reuse, either openly or under certain conditions, usually via a repository). Data licensing refers to the legal terms and conditions that govern the access and use of research data. Data reuse refers to the use of existing data for new purposes, such as analysis, synthesis, or validation. Many funding bodies in Australia, including the ARC and NHMRC, have mandates for open data as a condition of funding - which require researchers to make their data (or at least their metadata) publicly available as soon as possible after the project is complete.

However, ‘Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse’ also poses some governance and data management challenges, especially when dealing with sensitive data (including personal or health information, ecological data about endangered species, commercial-in-confidence data, or culturally sensitive data). Researchers and institutions need to ensure that they protect the privacy and confidentiality of their participants as outlined in [Privacy, Ethics and Data Residency](#) including compliance with privacy related legislation and research guidance. Sharing and reuse of data related to Indigenous peoples must also respect the rights and interests of the data owners or custodians in line with existing guidance such as the AIATSIS code of ethics² and CARE principles⁷.

‘Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse’ for Australian research data involves balancing the benefits of openness and collaboration with the risks of privacy breaches, consent requirements, Indigenous decision making, and intellectual property infringement. The core recommendations can be broken down into the themes of **data sharing**, **data publishing and reuse**, and **licencing and intellectual property**. Researchers need to be supported to adopt good data practices that enable them to share their data responsibly and ethically, while also respecting the rights and interests of others.

Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse: **Data Sharing**

Data sharing is an integral part of the research process, it is vital for collaboration, accelerates scientific discovery, and maximises return on investment in research. However, the sharing of sensitive research data requires additional consideration to mitigate the risks associated with re-identification and misuse.

- Provide access to secure research environments to enable the safe sharing of sensitive data. This includes the use of dedicated secure servers, encrypted transmission protocols, and strict access controls (as described in [Cyber Security: Protection and Prevention](#)) to ensure that only authorised individuals can access the data, that data is used appropriately and that no data can enter the environment or be removed without permission.
 - + Mandate the use of secure research data sharing environments, which can limit data access to approved researchers and purposes, log data access and use, and facilitate the secure analysis or transfer of data.
- Implement comprehensive de-identification processes in line with best practice standards, such as ISO/IEC 20889¹⁹, which provides guidelines for privacy enhancing data de-identification. Training should be provided to researchers on the application of these standards to their data sets.

- Establish a system for managing re-identification risk. This could include a combination of technical measures (such as anonymisation techniques), legal measures (such as data sharing agreements), and procedural measures (such as data access committees).
- Introduce rigorous risk management strategies to evaluate and mitigate the potential of re-identification and misuse of sensitive data. This may involve conducting privacy impact assessments and adopting a 'privacy by design' approach to all research projects involving sensitive data.
- Establish clear governance structures for mediated access to sensitive data. This could include a data access committee that reviews and approves requests for access, as well as a data steward who is responsible for managing the data throughout its lifecycle.
- Encourage researchers to consider data sharing at the earliest stages of their research, and to incorporate data sharing plans into their research proposals and consent/ethics processes. This will help to ensure that data sharing is considered as an integral part of the research process, rather than an afterthought.
 - + Provide training and support for researchers on using secure research data sharing environments, including guidance on how to de-identify data, how to manage re-identification risk, and how to comply with relevant laws and ethical guidelines.

Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse: **Data Sharing Agreements**

Data sharing is the practice of making research data accessible to others for review, collaboration, or further analysis, often supported by a formal data sharing agreement and potentially mediated within a secure research data sharing environment.

- Provide standard templates for data sharing agreements that support collaboration with external entities or institutions. Ensure these templates clarify data ownership, usage rights (including any outputs), security and data protection requirements, responsibilities, and timeframes.
 - + For sensitive data, use of a data sharing agreement should be mandated, and additional support, such as legal or ethics expertise, should be accessible to researchers.
 - + Legal review of data sharing agreements required for sharing data classified as Red.
- Develop a process for Indigenous data sharing agreements, which respects the principles such as the AIATSIS Code of Ethics² and CARE⁷. These agreements should focus on community engagement, obtaining consent for sharing, and ensuring that benefits flow back to Indigenous communities.
- Develop guidelines or provide legal support for data sharing across jurisdictions, incorporating the relevant restrictions and requirements of both countries.
 - + For sensitive data, implement processes that regularly check for compliance of any cross-jurisdictional data sharing arrangements.
- Provide processes to ensure data sharing agreements are negotiated early in the research process, to provide clarity of ownership, rights and responsibilities, intellectual property, and the right to publish and reuse data.

Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse: **Data Publishing and Reuse**

Funding agencies and research stakeholders are increasingly pushing towards methodologies that support and encourage open data and data reuse. Data publishing is underpinned by the FAIR principles¹⁵ (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), which means that data should be well-described, stored in reliable repositories, compatible with other data sources, and easy to use and cite. However, researchers need to be supported to meet these obligations while also ensuring sensitive data are appropriately managed and protected.

Institutions should ensure researchers are provided access to repositories that employ the TRUST principles²⁰ (transparent, responsible, user-friendly, sustainable, and technologically robust) following guidance provided by the ARDC (<https://ardc.edu.au/resource/trust-principles>).

Additional guidance to support publishing and reuse of sensitive data is provided in the ARDC's [Publishing Sensitive Data](#)²¹ guide.

- Provide researchers with access to a set of defined repositories for data publishing. These may be institutional or national/international discipline specific repositories. A high-quality discipline-specific repository may be preferred, especially for large datasets or where specific curation or quality control is required. Additional guidance is provided by the ARDC (<https://ardc.edu.au/resource/guide-to-choosing-a-data-repository/>). Enhancements for sensitive data include:
 - + Restrict data publishing options to specific repositories, considering requirements such as licensing and [Data Residency and Jurisdiction](#).
 - + Have a two-step or independently verified approval process to ensure data are not published without approval or use a repository with an automated sensitivity checking process.
 - + Ensure the repository meets the required cyber security standards for the data sensitivity (as described in [Cyber Security – Protection and Prevention](#)) such as [Encryption](#) in transit/at rest and appropriate [Access Controls](#).
 - + Ensure the repository features ongoing mechanisms to check [Data Integrity](#).
 - + Publish metadata only (if appropriate and required) for highly sensitive/Red data. These data should have their sensitivity reduced (such as by deidentification, anonymisation) prior to any publishing consideration or use a repository with an appropriate level of mediated access.
- Establish a clear policy and process for takedown requests to ensure that the rights of data subjects are respected, while also protecting the institution from potential legal risks. The policy should outline the circumstances under which data may be removed or access restricted, the process for submitting a takedown request, and the process for reviewing and actioning such requests. It should also provide for an appeals process. This policy should be clearly communicated to all researchers and data users.
- Ensure that data repositories used for the storage and sharing of Indigenous data are culturally safe, respect the rights of Indigenous peoples, and are in line with the relevant guidelines such as the AIATSIS code of ethics².

- Support FAIR data practices¹⁵ by ensuring published data are accessible through being assigned a persistent identifier (such as a digital object identifier or DOI) and are accompanied by comprehensive metadata (findable). Metadata should include information such as the creator, date, format, and any associated licenses or restrictions.
- For sensitive data, ensure the accompanying metadata captures all relevant approval details such as human or animal ethics, and that the sensitivity classification of the data is clearly identifiable.
- For published research datasets involving human subjects, ensure metadata highlights any permissions and/or constraints from participants for their data to be available for reuse in future complementary research. Researchers should be provided with training to ensure that licence agreements chosen for published datasets take these permissions into account.

Data Sharing, Licensing, and Reuse: **Licensing and Intellectual Property**

The general recommendations from the open access policies of the ARC and NHRMC and FAIR¹⁵ data principles are that research data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. This means that data should be published for reuse with the least restrictive licence possible, unless there are ethical, legal, data residency or commercial reasons to limit access or use.

Intellectual property (IP) is also an important consideration for data sharing and reuse, especially in the context of protecting IP through licensing. The National Principles of Intellectual Property Management for Publicly Funded Research²² provide specific guidelines and requirements. While these intersect with data reuse (such as the need to consider the IP rights of others when reusing existing data), they also cover broader IP management themes which are outside the current scope of the Decoder.

Note: recommendations for licence considerations primarily pertain to data classified and Green to Yellow, but that may have been derived from sensitive data. Sensitive data itself should not be licensed and exposed as open access.

- Encourage the use of standardised licences for data sharing or publishing (of non-sensitive data), such as Creative Commons (CC) licences, providing clarity on what the licence allows others to do with the data. Institutions should provide guidance on the differences between licences and mechanisms to ensure researchers choose the one that aligns with their sharing intentions. For example, Creative Commons provides a [simple and interactive questionnaire](#) to help identify the appropriate CC licence.
 - + An open access licence that enables the maximum potential for reuse is usually preferred for research data (typically [CC BY](#) or equivalent) however licences that have more restrictive terms should be considered for data with any degree of sensitivity.
 - + For data with cultural or community significance, engage with relevant stakeholders to determine appropriate licensing models.
 - + Expert advice and support for licensing and data publishing should be made accessible to researchers licensing data derived from sensitive data.
 - + Ensure that metadata for these datasets includes clear licensing details, any restrictions on use, and contacts for further clarifications or permissions.
 - + Regular audits for adherence to licensing terms should be considered for data with any sensitivity.

- Offer resources or access to expertise to guide researchers in identifying and distinguishing between various types of IP rights, such as copyright, patents, trademarks, and trade secrets, especially as they pertain to research data. Provide this advice throughout the research process not just at the point of invention disclosure.
- Establish processes to support researchers who are seeking to use third-party sensitive data, which may include internal cross-checking, standardised approval processes and legal assessments.

Cyber Security – Protection and Prevention

The cyber security controls and guidelines delineated in the following sections are derived from the Australian ISM¹², and internationally recognised governance instruments such as the NIST framework (including special publications 800-53rev5²³, and 800-171r3²⁴) and ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴, although these same recommendations appear in many other cybersecurity frameworks and guidelines. These frameworks provide a comprehensive set of principles and recommendations tailored for securing sensitive data, and they have been adapted here to suit the specific requirements and nuances associated with protecting sensitive research data.

The core cyber security recommendations related to ‘protection and prevention’ can be subset into five key thematic areas – **access controls**, **data encryption**, **endpoint protection**, **network segmentation**, and **data loss prevention**. By implementing stringent measures within these thematic areas, ‘protection and prevention’ aims to create a robust first line of defence that not only deters potential attackers but also adds complexity and resource-intensive hurdles to any malicious attempts to compromise data. In the context of sensitive research data, the focus is on preserving the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information, ensuring research integrity and that the privacy and safety of individuals associated with the data are maintained.

Adherence to these cyber security frameworks, or the principles outlined within them, also supports many of the obligations around data protection, access restrictions and integrity outlined in the Australian research integrity frameworks such as the Code²⁻⁶, as well as other relevant legal instruments such as Australian Privacy Principle 11 “Security of personal information”¹⁸.

Cyber Security: Access Controls

The management and control of user permissions, ensuring only authorised individuals can interact with sensitive data.

- Employ the principle of least privilege, limiting access based on job responsibilities (role-based access control).
 - + Enhancements include regular audits of access, automated offboarding, retaining records of sensitive data access.
- Implement robust password controls for all users such as using a lengthy passphrase.
 - + Enhancements include requiring two-factor authentication, or multi-factor authentication with the addition of biometrics or Fast IDentity Online ([FIDO](#)) Alliance certified authentication.
- Integrate Privileged Access Management (PAM) solutions to monitor and control elevated rights and streamline the management of privileged accounts.
- Utilise time-based access controls such as limiting the times during which users can access systems.
 - + Limiting the length of access may also be a consideration for highly sensitive data.

Cyber Security: **Data Encryption**

Encryption utilises algorithmic transformations to render data unreadable to unauthorised entities, preserving its integrity and confidentiality in digital ecosystems.

- Employ encryption (transforming readable data into an encrypted format that can only be accessed or deciphered by authorised parties who possess the appropriate cryptographic keys) of data in-transit.
 - + Enhancements include applying stronger encryption algorithms, perfect forward secrecy for sensitive communications to ensure past sessions remain secure.
- Employ encryption of data at rest
 - + Enhancements include applying stronger encryption algorithms and encrypting backup data not just primary data to reduce vulnerability.
- Utilise an encryption key management system.
 - + Regular audits of key management system, implementation of key rotation and key recovery protocols.
- Utilise virtual private networks (VPNs) for transmitting non-sensitive data over untrusted networks.
 - + Utilise end-to-end encryption for all sensitive communications.

Additional considerations include the utilisation of symmetric encryption (single key for both encryption and decryption) or asymmetric encryption (public and private key pairs) and where each might be more appropriate, as well as the option to employ, hardware-based encryption solutions for critical data, such as hardware security modules or trusted platform modules, which can offer additional security.

Cyber Security: **Endpoint Protection**

These protections work at the endpoint level to examine processes, system activity, and files for suspicious or malicious indicators as both an active response and at the preventative level.

- Employ and regularly update antivirus software on all endpoints.
 - + Implementation of an endpoint detection and response (EDR) solution with 24/7 monitoring on selected or all endpoints that are involved in Orange/Red research data.
- Prevent the use of unauthorised external devices or media.
 - + Ensure removable media policies and processes are limited to specific approved devices where their use is tracked and audited.
 - + Restrict the use of any removable devices on Orange/Red research data systems and employ only approved cloud-based data transfer options at the sensitive level.
- Implement device control and mobile device management.
 - + Implement an automated asset inventory management discovery tool (a system that continuously scans the network to identify and catalogue every device connected to it) to ensure that all devices are officially recognised and managed, reducing the risk of 'shadow IT', or the use of unauthorised devices and software.

- Use application whitelisting (limited to pre-approved software) on all endpoints to ensure only approved software and access rights can be utilised.
 - + Utilise a zero-trust security architecture (which has applicability beyond endpoint protection); a security approach that trusts no one by default and verifies every access request, regardless of where it comes from within or outside the institution.

Cyber Security: **Network Segmentation**

Network Segmentation involves partitioning a network into discrete sections to control data flow and reduce potential attack vectors, enhancing overall system resilience.

- Utilise internal network zones to separate different types of data or research activities.
 - + Use an air-gapped solution that separates sensitive data or sensitive research activity into an isolated physical and logical network segment.
- Utilise network firewalls to control traffic.
 - + Network firewalls can limit traffic to allow specific IPs or ports that required for the research project and block all other traffic.
 - + Deploy an intrusion prevention system which utilises advanced signature-based detections to determine which traffic is allowed or blocked.
- Keep development and production environments separate.
 - + Separation of development and production environments is to be utilised to test new configurations or code without affecting production data or systems until bugs and issues have been identified and resolved.
 - + Write-access to production environments should be limited and changes made need to conform to configuration management procedures. Development environments should not host real production data.
- Enhance network visibility and incident response with Network Detection and Response (NDR) tools, to monitor network traffic and respond to suspicious activities in real time.

Cyber Security: **Data Loss Prevention**

Data loss prevention (DLP) employs strategic controls and technologies to monitor and restrict the access, transfer, or deletion of sensitive information outside of authorised boundaries.

- Implement controls to detect and prevent unauthorised data transfers.
 - + Enhance by implementing a machine learning based DLP solution for real-time, risk-based monitoring of data transmission.
- Employ content filtering on email and web traffic to identify and prevent potential sensitive data transfers.
 - + An enhancement for highly sensitive or Red data would be to monitor and control all methods of data transfer.
- Use outbound traffic restrictions to known malicious sites.
 - + Enhance by limiting and restricting all outgoing traffic that is not explicitly required for business functionality.

Cyber Security – Detection and Response

The second core category of cyber security recommendations that are common across the major frameworks such as ISM¹², NIST¹³ and ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴ is 'detection and response' - encompassing **audit and monitoring** and **incident response planning**. This category offers a robust framework for identifying potential vulnerabilities, monitoring system activities for anomalous behaviours, and ensuring timely and effective action in the event of security breaches.

Also relevant to the Australian sensitive research data landscape in this element are the mandatory cyber incident notification requirements for research deemed 'critical' under the 2021 amendment²⁵ to the SOCI Act¹⁰, state-based privacy laws, and the 'Notifiable Data Breaches' scheme in the Privacy Act 1988 (Cth), as well as the constraints of external jurisdictions (if they apply) such as GDPR⁹.

These proactive and reactive measures are essential considerations for sensitive data protection, but they also support institutions to maintain the public trust in research data management. Implementing these recommendations supports data integrity, but also prepares institutions and researchers for stakeholder and participant engagement in the event of a data breach.

Cyber Security: **Auditing and Monitoring**

Constant vigilance of systems, networks, and user behaviour to detect any anomalies, intrusions, or policy violations.

- Utilise proactive network and vulnerability scanning. Enhancements include:
 - + Subscribe to public threat intelligence feeds.
 - + Periodic system, vulnerability, and network scanning to identify any vulnerabilities or irregularities.
 - + Utilise advanced solutions like Endpoint Detection and Response to identify and stop threats in real-time.
- Ensure that security-relevant logs are collected from all critical systems.
 - + For highly sensitive data ensure logs are backed-up and archived for review if needed
- Use security information and event management (SIEM) systems to aggregate and correlate logs, aiding in detecting anomalies. Enhancements include:
 - + Use tools that offer real-time monitoring of systems and networks for immediate threat detection and mitigation.
 - + Engage with advanced threat intelligence platforms or vendors for tailored insights and early warnings.
 - + Advanced signature and behaviour-based detections – AI based platforms.
 - + Engage with an external third-party 24/7 security operations centre (SOC) to monitor and respond to incidents in real-time.
- Monitor standard user and system activity to establish a behavioural baseline.
 - + Implement 'user and entity behaviour analytics' to monitor standard user and system activity to create a baseline and detect unusual patterns against this baseline.
- Conduct regular security audits to assess the effectiveness of controls.
 - + Engage a third-party for independent security testing and review.

Cyber Security: Incident Response Planning

Ensures that when an incident does occur, there is a clear plan and capability in place to respond effectively, minimising damage and ensuring a timely recovery.

- Establish a basic incident response plan that outlines steps to take when a security incident occurs.
 - + Develop an in-house or third-party forensics capability to deep dive into security incidents.
- Have a designated team or individual responsible for managing security incidents.
 - + Engage with an external third-party security operations centre to monitor and respond to incidents in real-time.
 - + Sign up for incident response retainers to assist in handling sophisticated security attacks and effectively respond to major security incidents.
- Ensure there is a protocol for internal communication and responses during and after an incident. Enhancements may include:
 - + Where the incident represents a notifiable breach, ensure mandatory notification requirements are completed, ideally by following a well-established internal procedure as described in [Privacy and Confidentiality](#).
 - + Conduct tabletop exercises to ensure everyone knows their roles during an incident.
 - + Develop a strategy for communicating with external stakeholders, media, and regulators as required.
- Institutes should develop a procedure for complying with critical infrastructure legislation (the SOCI Act^{10,25}) and have a clear understanding of how to identify, store and monitor any research data that could be deemed 'critical' under this Act. The procedure should detail the mandatory cyber incident notification requirements under the Act, and clearly identify who is responsible for making these notifications. This process should be cross-referenced with the institute's privacy-related data breach procedure as described in [Privacy and Confidentiality](#).

Cyber Security – Maintenance and Governance

Cyber security recommendations for maintenance and governance form the backbone of an institution's defence against threats, ensuring data protection, operational continuity, and compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.

The core cyber security recommendations related to 'maintenance and governance' from the relevant frameworks (including ISM¹², NIST¹³ and ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴) include proactive cyber security practices such as **configuration management**, **patch management**, and **backup and recovery**.

The final two categories - **employee training and awareness**, and **compliance and governance** - cut across and support all the previously mentioned physical and cyber security recommendations.

Cyber Security: Configuration Management

Configuration management involves the secure setup and maintenance of systems and software.

- Establish secure baseline configurations for all systems and software.
 - + Use automated tools to detect deviations from baseline configurations.
- Implement a change management process to oversee modifications to systems and applications.
- Conduct periodic reviews of system setups to ensure they remain secure.
 - + Prioritise the review of systems handling sensitive data, ensuring they are audited more frequently.
 - + Engage third-party specialists to conduct independent security assessments specifically for configurations that involve sensitive data.
- Maintain a secure backup strategy for configurations, especially those related to sensitive data storage and handling.
 - + Ensure that backups are encrypted and stored in secure locations, both on-site and off-site (see [Backup and Recovery](#)).
 - + Regularly test the restore process to ensure quick recovery in case of misconfigurations or breaches.

Cyber Security: Patch Management

Patch management covers the importance of keeping software and systems up to date to ensure vulnerabilities are addressed.

- Implement scheduled patching to regularly update software, operating systems, and applications to the latest versions.
 - + Enhancement: Use systems that automatically deploy patches when they become available.
- Implement periodic assessments to identify unpatched vulnerabilities. Enhancements include:
 - + Ensure patches for critical vulnerabilities are applied immediately.
 - + Engage third-party services for vulnerability assessments, specifically targeting software and systems associated with sensitive data handling.

- Establish a rollback strategy to revert any patch that may inadvertently introduce issues, particularly for systems handling sensitive data. This should include regular backups of configurations before patching to ensure rapid recovery in the event of complications.
 - + Automate the backup process to ensure consistent and timely backups and reducing the risk of human error. This automation should be monitored and regularly reviewed to ensure its effectiveness and reliability.

Cyber Security: **Backup and Recovery**

Ensuring data can be restored after adverse events, ranging from accidental deletions to malicious attacks.

- Perform regular backups of all essential data.
 - + Implement solutions that continuously back up data as it changes.
- Periodically test backups to ensure data integrity and restore capability.
 - + Encrypt backups and store in multiple separate physical locations to protect against localised threats.

Cyber Security: **Employee Training and Awareness**

Ensuring staff are aware of security threats and best practices. It is important to ensure this involves engaging with the relevant subject matter experts (ie Privacy Officer, CISO etc).

- Conduct regular basic security awareness training for all staff.
 - + Provide in-depth training for staff in critical roles or handling sensitive data.
- Train employees on recognising and responding to phishing attempts, social engineering, and other behavioural vulnerabilities.
 - + Further test employees by running fake phishing and social engineering scenarios.

Cyber Security: **Compliance and Governance**

Supporting the adherence to legal, regulatory, and best practice standards related to cybersecurity.

- Establish clear cybersecurity policies and guidelines based on industry best practices.
 - + Implement tools and practices that continuously monitor for compliance such as compliance management software.
- Establish formal governance roles and forums, as well as a risk management program, to continuously manage any identified risks.
- Periodically review systems and practices against established policies and regulatory standards.
 - + Engage third-party auditors to review and validate compliance efforts.

Physical Security

Physical security controls are discussed in detail in security frameworks such as NIST 1.0¹³ (SP 800-53 Revision 5²³), the ISM¹², and ISO/IEC 27001¹⁴ (Annex A.11). The controls described and recommended in these frameworks are broad ranging. Any implementation needs to consider local requirements and should be guided by a risk assessment.

In general, physical controls relate to three main areas – a **secure perimeter** and practical approaches taken to restrict access to infrastructure (fences, security guards, CCTV monitoring), **behavioural approaches** designed to empower staff to minimise data exposure and physical access risks (such as locking screens when not in use or preventing tailgating into secure areas) and **policies/procedures and documented processes** to ensure understanding of and compliance with the requirements. These physical security measures primarily relate to digital assets, but can be applied to securing analogue data such as paper records or primary materials.

While physical security measures may not be explicitly specified within other governance instruments such as the Australian Code⁶ or the National Statement⁵, safeguarding and controlling access to physical locations where data is stored or analysed (be that research labs, data centres, or archives) prevents unauthorised personnel from gaining direct access to, tampering with, or inadvertently compromising research data. Furthermore, physical security measures align with the Code's broader ethical principles by ensuring that research data, especially when it pertains to human subjects, remains protected from breaches of confidentiality or misuse. In essence, while not explicitly specified, physical security is integral to the overarching objective of research governance in Australia, which is to uphold the highest standards of data protection, integrity, and ethical conduct in research.

Physical Security: Perimeters, Access Controls, and Monitoring

The recommendations for physical security in each of these frameworks begin with establishing a secure perimeter – and increasing the specificity and access controls of that perimeter with increasing data sensitivity. For low-risk data that could simply mean swipe-card entry onto campus, but for higher-risk/sensitive data the perimeter should be defined more specifically, down to an individual datacentre or even a room containing a single instrument, with much more restricted access controls such as multi-factor authentication and remote monitoring of the entry point.

- Establish clear boundaries to protect data generation or storage infrastructure, using barriers like fences, walls, and controlled access points. Enhancements include:
 - + Increased specificity of the perimeter – down to specific buildings housing data related infrastructure or even down to one specific room or locked rack
 - + Implementation of additional physical barriers such as reinforced doors or bollards.
 - + Implementation of anti-tailgating entry mechanisms.
 - + Air-gapped environments
- Control and monitor all entry and exit points to ensure only authorised individuals can enter secure areas. Enhancements include:
 - + Implement electronic access control systems, such as card readers or biometric systems, to allow only authorised personnel entry. Further enhancements for sensitive data include the use of two-factor authentication on entry points and retaining an audit log of access.

- + CCTV surveillance of entry points is recorded (for low sensitivity data) or active CCTV monitor (for high sensitivity or Red data).
 - + Physical security guards available on site. Enhancement for sensitive data include security guards monitoring physical access to the perimeter to detect and respond to physical security incidents.
 - + Utilisation of alarm systems for unapproved entry, environmental monitoring, tampering etc.
- Implement equipment security to protect equipment or data from environmental damage, theft, tampering, and unauthorised access. Enhancements include:
 - + Secure equipment in place such as by locking devices to desks or storing data or equipment in lockable cabinets or racks.
 - + Lock physical devices and media containing information in secure containers, rooms, or areas when not in use and protect such devices and media from unauthorised physical access, tampering, theft, or destruction.
 - + Provide controls for equipment taken off-site to ensure they are secure.
 - + Ensure facilities and equipment are protected against environmental threats like fires, floods, and storms through monitoring and alarms.

Physical Security: **Behavioural Approaches**

Behavioural approaches focus on influencing and managing human actions to enhance the security of physical assets and spaces.

- Ensure workstations and devices lock or time out when left unattended.
 - + Manually lock screens, devices or containers storing physical data immediately when not in use.
 - + Implement clear desk and clear screen policies to ensure sensitive data are inaccessible when not in use.
- Implement secure disposal methods for sensitive information or equipment (see also [Data Retention and Destruction](#)).
 - + For sensitive data, obtain official certification of disposal if utilising a third party for this service.
- Provide awareness training to protect against unwanted physical security risk behaviours such as tailgating into secure access areas.
 - + Enhancement includes ensuring staff credentials are clearly displayed at all times.

Additional considerations for physical documents include providing shredders and locked waste containers for physical data destruction, adding an access layer to photocopiers and printers (i.e. pin or swipe card access) and providing locked storage for physical data assets (with similar recommendations for other physical security measures as those for infrastructure hosting Orange/Red data).

Physical Security: **Policies/Procedures and Documented Processes**

Policies/procedures and documented processes provide a structured framework for safeguarding physical assets through established guidelines and systematic actions.

- Develop, approve, and maintain a list of individuals with authorised access to the secure perimeter or facility where the system resides, and issue authorisation credentials for perimeter/facility access.
 - + Enhancements include restricting access to a limited number of people, role-based, regular review, and clear on-boarding and off-boarding processes.
- Implement procedures for authorising and monitoring visitors (including contractors and support staff) - including visitor logs, escorted access, and visitor badges.
- Periodically review and maintain physical security measures to ensure they are up-to-date and effective.
- Provide regular training around current physical access controls and requirements to individuals with authorised access.

Final observations/conclusions

Institutional approaches to sensitive data management – the ‘Landscape Report’ and the foundation of the Decoder

Prior to developing the Decoder, we surveyed six Australian universities to understand the variation in institutional approaches to sensitive data management. This process was designed to inform the development of the Decoder and to identify maturity levels and challenges related to sensitive data governance in research. The resulting Landscape Report¹⁷, revealed some shared practices in sensitive data management. However, it also highlighted a prevalent commonality in the challenges faced when implementing the range of requirements and recommendations to protect and manage sensitive research data - irrespective of the approach undertaken. These challenges can broadly be aligned to four key categories: People, Policy, Process and Product/Technology (outlined in Table 1 below). It is important to note that while Table 1 underscores the commonalities, it also highlights the nuances required to improve current implementation practices. It is also important to note that effective improvement in all these areas will require sustained executive support and adequate financial investment.

Table 1: Elements identified in the Landscape Report¹⁷ as impacting the complexity of institutional approaches to sensitive research data management.

People	Engagement across all stakeholders from leadership and governance structures through to researchers and higher degree students was identified as necessary for the execution of effective sensitive research data governance. Governance groups are distributed, and structures are varied depending on the Institution. Size, composition, and delegations of high-level governance groups are extremely diversified, and it is clear the spectrum of controls is required to be clearly articulated. They also have downflow effects on how sensitive research data management controls are implemented. For example, for training to be mandatory and provided to all relevant researchers, significant buy-in from all areas of an institution would be required. Technological, process and people changes would all need to be implemented.
Policy	The recent introduction of the Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022 (Cth) ¹¹ and associated framework for sharing Australian Government data (DATA Scheme) has triggered a wholistic look at sensitive research data management, governance, and practices within academic institutions. The DATA Scheme application process has put a spotlight on the complexities of institutional decision making and the various roles and responsibilities involved.
Process	A further complicating factor for governance processes is the requirement for compliance with standards. Governance structures need to be able to cater for different standards requirements for different types of data, which is very difficult to achieve if these same processes are applied to both enterprise and research data requirements.
Product/Technology	The complex nature of research data and rapid changes in technology also makes improving the usability and design of research data management processes and systems difficult. System design needs to balance the critical nature of data governance and security requirements

	with ease of use for researchers. Current system and process design surveyed institutions has shown critical gaps, which has highlighted that the risk of data disclosure is not seen as significant enough to encourage researchers to use appropriate workflows. Future infrastructure solutions that strike an appropriate balance between protection and ease of use for the researcher is therefore essential to ensure higher uptake among researchers.
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There were two key elements of the Landscape Report¹⁷ that informed the development of the Decoder.

1. **Intended Audience:** Our research revealed that decision-making processes concerning sensitive research data within institutions are widely varied, lacking consistency across different organisations. This insight was pivotal in pinpointing institutional decision-makers as the primary audience for the Decoder.
2. **Harmonisation of Decision-Making Across Four Key Areas (People, Policy, Process, Product/Technology):** The Landscape Report¹⁷ highlighted the need to harmonised decision-making across these four areas. This understanding shaped the Decoder's structure. It serves as an initial step towards fostering a shared understanding of the extensive scope and complexity inherent in governance and data protection guidelines related to sensitive research data across multiple areas. While these elements are often separated within institutions, the requirements impacting people and policies through to technological controls are not mutually exclusive, and the Decoder begins to elucidate their interdependence.

Institutional decision making

The governance landscape influencing sensitive research data management in Australia is broad and complex. Academic and research institutions must ensure their management and protection of sensitive research data complies with a vast array of legal, ethical, social, financial, and technical requirements. As noted in the Landscape Report¹⁷, there is also no single leadership role responsible for the totality of decision making to ensure institutions meet these obligations. Unlike other forms of sensitive data (such a business records), decision makers for research data often navigate a 'tug of war' of competing priorities. This includes balancing the imperatives of data preservation and reuse against the necessity of data destruction, advocating for open collaboration and FAIR¹⁵ data practices while upholding stringent privacy and security measures, and reconciling the need for standardised institutional protocols with the diverse and evolving nature of research. Adding to this complexity is increasing need to not just understand but actively embed Indigenous data sovereignty principles into practice, the pace of technological advancement influencing data generation and storage, and the increasing sophistication of cyber security threats. The Decoder provides an extensive yet accessible overview of key recommendations across the breadth of decision-making domains; to support informed, cohesive, and strategic decision making across all institutional roles and responsibilities.

The breadth of governance instruments influencing sensitive data are also not mutually exclusive. For instance, robust cyber security practices are foundational not only for data protection but are also pivotal for maintaining high standards in privacy, ethics, and data integrity, and yet these domains are often the responsibility of different institutional leadership roles.

The Decoder is designed to demystify the complex governance landscape impacting sensitive research data, providing a comprehensive guide for institutional decision makers to work together to navigate the interplay of legal obligations, funding body guidelines, community best practices, and evolving cyber security standards.

Supporting the development of training and guidance

The need to provide researchers with more training and guidance around sensitive data management was evident in the institutional responses in the Landscape Report¹⁷, where we identified that there was very little centrally managed training dedicated to sensitive data management, with the reliance primarily falling to generalised cyber security training for upskilling researchers on 'sensitive data' management principles. Additionally, there is a need to provide leaders and decision makers with training in best practice implementations, whether that is around the development of policies, procedures and guidance documents or the implementation of software and hardware solutions for research data applications.

Specific recommendations for training and guidance are only briefly mentioned in the elements of the Decoder, as this element of sensitive data management and protection is rarely specifically called out in governance requirements. However, in practice, good quality training and guidance is necessary to ensure the successful implementation and utilisation of most recommendations and controls designed to protect and responsibly manage sensitive data.

The Decoder can be utilised to guide institutions to develop and implement targeted training in the areas of highest risk, for example sensitive data handling training or intensive cyber security safety modules targeted towards researchers working with highly sensitive or Red data.

As a future step, the Decoder can form the framework for the development generalised and nationally relevant sensitive data handling and data management training, potentially through initiatives such as the ARDC supported [PAI-C](#) training project or as part of the [People Research Data Commons](#). The Decoder can provide the scaffold to support the structure of modules addressing each of the core elements that were identified from the governance landscape, such as Data Sharing, Licensing and Reuse.

The balance between cyber security and research practice

In the Landscape Report¹⁷ most institutions reported some alignment of research systems to industry cyber security standards, occasionally including formal accreditations such as ISO/IEC 27001¹⁹, however these processes and responsibilities were rarely research focussed. There was also significant variation across institutions regarding the processes to assess specific controls required for different levels of data sensitivity or data classification categories.

On some levels the guidelines for the cyber and physical security elements of the Decoder are the most straightforward and consistent to present in the Decoder format, based on the consistency across various security frameworks such as NIST¹³ or the Australasian ISM¹². These, however, are also the elements that are often the least well understood by decision makers from research domains, even though they are essential to supporting privacy and ethical compliance obligations.

The difference between the presentation of these security elements in the Decoder and their usual format is that the Decoder uses the lens of data sensitivity to showcase examples of best practice controls, with enhancements for highly sensitive data. Cyber security controls are usually presented in a format designed to ensure that the integrity and confidentiality of data are maintained, regardless of its sensitivity level.

Figure 1. A hypothetical mapping of security controls against data classification levels

Cyber security decision makers could use the Decoder to demonstrate to researchers which controls are necessary to implement for different data classification levels, taking into account institutional risk appetite and the technical viability of the relevant systems.

For example, in Figure 1 shows a *hypothetical* implementation map of some of the controls outlined in [Cyber Security – Protection and Prevention](#), with different controls applied for different classes of data (Green to Red). In this hypothetical scenario, basic incident response processes are applied as the baseline for all data (Green) through to the utilisation of a third-party security operations centre for Red data. Institutions would need to assess these controls against their risk appetite to determine where to apply enhancements (for example another institution might apply a 24/7 SOC for Orange data).

This kind of control to data classification mapping could help bridge the gap between the researchers and security professionals. Researchers become more aware of the security imperatives tied to different data classification, grasping why certain data requires more stringent protective measures. Simultaneously, security professionals can gain a better understanding of the need for researchers to access, share, and collaborate on data. This approach facilitates collaborative decision-making and ensures that data management strategies provide robust security without unduly hinder research processes.

Future directions

While the Decoder is a starting point towards developing a central reference for institutions and researchers, simplifying the complexities of the numerous frameworks, governance tools, and legislative requirements affecting research data management, is it also **only able to provide a ‘moment in time’ view**. The governance landscape around sensitive research data continues to evolve, and the information in the Decoder will also need to adapt and update to keep pace. On the near-term horizon are incoming changes to the Privacy Act and the release of NIST 2.0, both of which will have an impact on institutional decision making around sensitive data protections. We hope this document can provide both a call to action for the framework of the Decoder to be used to develop a ‘living’ reference for institutions – possibly in the form of a regularly updated document or website.

Throughout this project we identified a variety of elements required for effective institutional change in sensitive research data management. Due to the time limitations, many of these elements could not be addressed directly or in sufficient detail in either the Decoder or the Landscape Report. These elements requiring additional consideration or work are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Elements of sensitive data management identified as requiring additional consideration or work.

People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanisms for institutional decision making regarding sensitive research data e.g. governance bodies, accountable individuals • Defined roles and responsibilities for all relevant stakeholders e.g. the University as a whole, different organisational units, accountable individuals, principal investigators, researchers etc. • Strategic direction and alignment between relevant stakeholders • Collaboration between relevant stakeholders • Training and guidance roll out to researchers • Communication plans for engagement with researchers • Appropriate and adequate support teams for researchers
Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of a research data classification framework • Clear definitions of sensitive data
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better project metadata management and monitoring to identify sensitive data projects • Auditing, reporting or oversight of sensitive data projects • Providing Standard Operating Procedures to researchers
Product/Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalogues of systems and services available • Decision making tools to aid researchers in data classification or selection of systems and services • Standardised mechanisms of assessing system security and appropriateness for sensitive data • Technology suitable for sensitive research data, including protected research environments

Within each of these areas there will be nuance in how they can be implemented for different data classification levels, or to satisfy different institutional risk appetites. For example, the People element '**Training and guidance roll out to researchers**' might take the form of a range of implementations; from provision of learning resources with no recorded completions, to voluntary enrolment into training with recorded completions, right through to compulsory training of all staff with regular recompletion required. Based on risk appetite, an institution might choose to require mandatory training only for researchers handling highly sensitivity or Red data.

The priority, feasibility, and impact of implementing these elements will also vary between universities. Future expansion of the work of the Decoder into a more detailed expression of each of these areas could create a resource in the style of a 'capability maturity model' to guide institutional decision makers in sensitive data management - and is a potential expansion of the work started in this project. Coordinated workshopping and national consultation would be required to reach a position that would be valuable to a broad range of institutions but would provide a tool to harmonise and benchmark institutional practice across the sector.

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Appendix 1 – Relevant Governance Instruments

Australian Research-Specific Guidance:

Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research 2018: This code outlines the responsibilities and principles for ethical, honest, and conscientious research in Australia.

Supplementary guides supporting implementation of the Code: These guides provide more detailed and practical advice on how to comply with the Code in specific areas of research, such as authorship, data management, peer review, and conflicts of interest.

National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research 2023: This statement provides a series of guidelines for investigators, review bodies and institutions regarding the ethical conduct of research involving human participants. It covers all aspects of the design, review, and conduct of human research in Australia.

Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and communities: These guidelines provide a set of principles to ensure that research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and communities is safe, respectful, responsible, high quality, and beneficial.

AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research, 2020: This code embodies the best practice standards of ethical research with and about Indigenous peoples. It requires researchers to respect Indigenous peoples' rights, interests, values, cultures, and aspirations.

Indigenous Cultural Protocols for Producing Indigenous Australian Music, Writing, Visual Arts, Media Arts and Performing Arts: These protocols provide guidance for researchers who access, use, or reproduce Indigenous cultural materials or involve Indigenous peoples in their research. The protocols aim to ensure that research is conducted with respect, recognition, and reciprocity.

Australian Research Council Research Integrity Policy, 2023: This policy outlines the requirements for institutions and individuals involved in ARC-funded research to report research integrity matters to the ARC, and the actions that the ARC may take in response to reported breaches of the Code.

Australian Code for the Care and Use of Animals for Scientific Purposes, 2013: This code promotes the ethical, humane, and responsible care and use of animals for scientific purposes. It covers all aspects of the design, review, and conduct of animal research in Australia. It also sets out the ethical framework and governing principles for animal research.

Other guidelines relating to the use of animals for scientific purposes: These guidelines provide additional information and advice for animal ethics committees and researchers on specific fields of research or types of animals. They should be read in conjunction with the Australian Code for the Care and Use of Animals for Scientific Purposes, 2013.

National principles of Intellectual Property management for publicly funded research: These principles aim to improve the commercial outcomes from publicly funded research by assisting researchers and institutions to identify, protect, and manage intellectual property.

Australian Legislation:

Privacy Act 1988: Governs the handling of personal information about individuals, including its collection, use, storage, and disclosure.

Australian Privacy Principles (APPs): Part of the Privacy Act, governs personal information handling.

Security of Critical Infrastructure Act (SOCI Act), 2018: This act aims to strengthen the security and resilience of critical infrastructure by capturing sectors and asset classes essential to Australia. It places obligations on responsible entities for certain critical infrastructure assets.

Security Legislation Amendment (Critical Infrastructure Protection) Bill, 2020: This amendment to the SOCI Act introduces mandatory cyber incident reporting requirements, specifies cyber security obligations, fosters collaboration, and ultimately protects critical infrastructure and essential services.

Data Availability and Transparency Act (DAT Act), 2020: This act implements a scheme to authorise and regulate access to Australian Government data. It authorises public sector data custodians to share data with accredited users in accordance with specific authorisations, purposes, principles and agreements.

Foreign Influence Transparency Scheme: Requires persons undertaking certain activities on behalf of a foreign principal to register and provide transparency about their relationship and activities.

Foreign Arrangements Scheme: Seeks to ensure that arrangements between Australian public universities and foreign entities do not harm Australia's foreign relations or are inconsistent with Australia's foreign policy.

Autonomous Sanctions Act 2011: Provides a framework for the Australian government to impose targeted financial and travel sanctions against persons and entities involved in grave international crimes or threats to international peace and security.

Defence Trade Controls Act, 2012: Regulates the export, supply, and publication of defence and strategic goods and technology.

Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act, 1999: Focuses on the protection of the environment and conservation of biodiversity.

National Health Security Act, 2007 and National Health Security Regulations, 2018: Establish a framework for national surveillance and response to communicable diseases and other health threats.

Security Sensitive Biological Agents standards: Set out requirements for entities that deal with certain biological agents that pose security risks.

Copyright Act, 1968: This act regulates the rights and obligations of copyright owners and users in Australia. It covers the protection of original and other works.

Australian/International Cyber Security Frameworks:

Australian Government's Protective Security Policy Framework (PSPF) and Information Security Manual (ISM): Provides policies and guidance for information protection. IRAP is a framework for assessing IT systems against the ISM/PSPF

ISO/IEC 27001: An international standard for information security management systems.

NIST: U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology framework, but widely referenced internationally.

***COBIT (Control Objectives for Information and Related Technologies):** An international framework for IT management and IT governance.

***Essential Eight** Australian cyber security framework comprising eight mitigation strategies to enhance organisational resilience against cyber threats and minimise the risk of data breaches.

***CIS (Center for Internet Security) Controls:** A prioritised set of actions that form a defence-in-depth set of best practices to mitigate the most common cyber attacks.

***Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) Guidelines:** International best practices for cloud security.

*These frameworks were used to determine the core 'elements' for cyber security frameworks in the Decoder

International or Multi-Jurisdictional Research Data recommendations:

FAIR Data Principles: FAIR principles advocate for research data to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable to promote scientific discovery and collaboration.

CARE Data Principles: CARE principles focus on the ethical stewardship of Indigenous data, emphasising Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics in data management.

Research Data Alliance (RDA) Recommendations: International outputs related to research data.

Privacy Frameworks Specific to Other Jurisdictions:

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018: An EU regulation for data processing involving EU citizens.

Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) 1996: An American standard for health data.

The Data Protection Act 2018: An implementation of the GDPR specific to the United Kingdom.

Australian State and territory-level regulations and frameworks (out of scope for direct consideration)

New South Wales (NSW):

- **Health Records and Information Privacy Act 2002:** Specific to the handling of health information, including research data related to health.
- **Privacy and Personal Information Protection Act 1988:** Governs the collection, use, and disclosure of personal information by NSW public sector agencies.

Victoria:

- **Privacy and Data Protection Act 2014:** Sets standards for the responsible collection and handling of personal information by Victorian public sector organizations.
- **Health Records Act 2001:** Addresses the privacy of health information in both the public and private sectors within Victoria.

Queensland:

- **Information Privacy Act 2009:** Applies to Queensland Government agencies and governs the collection and handling of personal information.
- **Hospital and Health Boards Act 2011:** Provides guidance on the management of health records, including research data.

South Australia:

- **Privacy Committee of South Australia:** Though South Australia does not have specific privacy legislation; the Privacy Committee issues guidelines that may impact the management of sensitive research data.

Western Australia:

- **Freedom of Information Act 1992:** While not directly related to privacy, it includes provisions related to the disclosure of information held by public bodies, which may affect research data.

Tasmania:

- **Personal Information Protection Act 2004:** Regulates the handling of personal information by Tasmanian public sector organizations.

Australian Capital Territory (ACT):

- **Health Records (Privacy and Access) Act 1997:** Governs the privacy of health records in the ACT.
- **Information Privacy Act 2014:** Applies to ACT public sector agencies and their handling of personal information.

Northern Territory:

- **Information Act 2002:** Governs the collection and handling of personal information by public sector organizations in the Northern Territory.